

Employability of the Bachelor of Elementary Graduates: A Trailblazer Study

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Abstract:

The study aimed to determine the employability of BEED graduates from Mandaue City College. This study used a quantitative and descriptive methodology to interpret the collected data. Stratified convenient sampling was utilized to ensure representative subject selection. The survey, administered via Google Forms, utilized frequency distribution, simple percentage, and weighted mean for data analysis. Key findings reveal a predominance of young, female respondents with a high involvement as observed in 2023. Motivations for pursuing teaching range from personal passion to familial influence and LET passing rates reflecting preparedness for teaching roles. It is clear from graduates' post-college training and diverse career paths beyond traditional teaching roles that BEED graduates are adaptable. It emphasizes the importance of LET passing rates as indicators of teaching readiness. Given the diversity of career paths pursued by BEED graduates, it emphasizes the importance of tailored career guidance and support services. Exploring employability skills through the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model adopted by Kurt (2019) reveals varying proficiency levels in technology and pedagogy, with strengths in literacy-related technologies and pedagogical skills. The study emphasizes the value of developing graduates' technical and soft skills to increase their employability and efficacy in teaching professions, and it recommends that the institution carry out assessments to guarantee skill development before graduation. Drawing from the Human Capital Theory of Cornillez et al. (2021) and the TPACK model of Kurt (2019), it is evident that skill acquisition expands employment opportunities for graduates. By implementing the recommended tool, the institution can produce internationally competitive graduates.

Keywords: Employability, BEED Graduates, Trailblazer Tracer Study, TPACK

Introduction:

In the current dynamic and competitive labor market, where change is an everyday reality, employability is critical in determining their capacity to secure and retain a job. It reduces the risk of job loss and the negative consequences associated with job instability, thereby increasing the likelihood that individuals can achieve their ambitions, goals, and aspirations. Donald et al. (2018) noted that employability is crucial for a long-term career, characterized by the ability to maintain one's current position or secure new employment when needed. Additionally, higher education provides students

with the skills required to build careers within their country, ensuring graduates can obtain their first job, sustain it, and move on to new opportunities. To effectively assess the distribution of graduates and evaluate how their training impacts job prospects, institutions should conduct tracer studies to enhance the employability of their graduates.

According to Danday (2023), the value of education was heavily reliant on the caliber of teachers employed within educational institutions. Hence, there was a pressing need for teacher education institutions to evaluate the competitiveness of their graduates within the teaching profession. This emphasis on teacher quality aligns with the findings of Abelha et al. (2020), who asserted that graduates' employability and competency enhancement hinges upon the effective implementation of innovative and collaborative practices within higher education. Furthermore, according to Lijueraj et al. (2019), graduate tracer studies were suitable for evaluating the outcomes of education and training offered by academic institutions. They provided essential details about the graduates' locations and employment statuses, providing valuable insights into the effectiveness of education and training programs for both graduates and employers. Integrating these perspectives emphasizes the importance of comprehensive evaluation methods, including graduate tracer studies, in assessing the effectiveness of teacher education programs and enhancing graduate employability in the teaching profession.

The absence of a tracer study within the School of Education presents a significant limitation in assessing the effectiveness of the program and the instructional strategies employed by the faculty. This deficiency underscores the necessity of conducting a tracer study to address fundamental inquiries concerning the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) graduates. These inquiries encompass ascertaining whether graduates acquired the skills imparted during their academic years, evaluating their employability rate, and comprehending the factors influencing their employment status. Consequently, the initiation of a tracer study was imperative to inform prospective enhancements to the educational curriculum and practices.

This research would determine the necessity of implementing an exit assessment for BEED graduates at Mandaue City College, which would serve as a road map for future graduates to enhance their employability, navigate their career paths, and achieve their professional goals effectively. It empowers individuals to take proactive steps toward securing meaningful employment and advancing their careers. In addition, this study would help the pre-service BEED teachers to enhance their skills and adapt to changing educational landscapes, ensuring they were well-prepared to meet the needs of a modern classroom and contribute effectively to the holistic progress of students.

Literature Review:

According to the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), in line with CHED memorandum order no.29 series of 2013, Supplemental implementing guidelines on cascading performance targets of state universities and colleges that committed to enhancing the quality and relevance of higher education in the Philippines, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) emphasizes the importance of conducting tracer studies. These studies are crucial for assessing the employability of graduates, understanding their career paths, and evaluating the effectiveness of academic programs.

Employability encompasses a range of qualities, from technical proficiency to soft skills and adaptability, that enable individuals to not only secure job opportunities but also excel in their chosen fields. According to Abelha et al. (2020), Higher education institutions were increasingly focusing on strategies that help students develop skills that enhance their chances of getting a job after graduation, often referred to as employability. It also encompasses accomplishments such as skills, understanding, and personal attributes that enhance individuals' prospects of securing employment and achieving success in their desired professions.

Demographic Data

Segbenya et al. (2022) found that employers prioritize three key skills in graduates: the capacity to work under pressure with minimal supervision, proficiency in IT applications, and technical expertise, with gender and educational attainment playing a substantial role in adopting these skills. Similarly, Majid et al. (2020) highlighted that demographic factors, such as location, significantly influence employment levels. Navarro et al. (2020) added that young people exhibit high levels of resources for employment and proactive behavior, alongside low job search difficulties. Moreover, Patimo et al. (2019) revealed that the location of graduates' residences strongly predicts their employability, particularly in the first six months post-graduation. These findings are supported by Bilal (2023), who argued that inefficient location choices by

employers exacerbate spatial unemployment differentials, and Conley (2020), who explored how spatial dynamics, including travel time and racial distribution, affect unemployment clustering, highlighting the importance of place-based policies to address these challenges.

Academic Profile

The academic profile of respondents encompasses achievements, including abilities, comprehension, and character traits that increase people's chances of landing a job and being successful in their chosen fields. This not only benefits the individuals themselves but also has positive implications for the workforce, the community, and the economy as a whole (Pubertal et al., 2023). As stated by Pardo Pichay (2019), education is essential for both national and personal development, with many individuals pursuing degrees to secure employment and a livelihood after graduation. To address issues like graduate unemployment, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) continuously monitors higher education institutions (HEIs) to ensure compliance with regional and global standards, focusing on graduate employability. Tentama et al. (2019) found a strong link between academic performance and self-concept in employability, while Li et al. (2022) noted that academic performance predicts employability by mediating achievement motivation. Atay (2023) further observed that receiving an honors degree boosts male graduates' salaries, particularly those from non-elite universities, but has no significant effect on female graduates' earnings.

Current Employment

Employability encompasses accomplishments such as skills, understanding, and personal attributes that enhance individuals' prospects of securing employment and achieving success in their desired professions. Individuals typically start at entry-level positions, such as Teacher 1, and progress in their careers as their skills develop (Abana et al., 2021). According to Mahid et al. (2019), skills are crucial for job hunting and fostering a productive, successful career path. The importance of soft skills, such as a positive attitude, effective communication, self-motivation, and problem-solving, is emphasized for enhancing employability (Asefer et al., 2021). Additionally, Yadav & Dhar (2021) explain that employees with more experience tend to perform better due to a larger foundation of knowledge, which aids in developing abilities for effective performance. Experience also plays a significant role in employability, as supported by Bohndick et al. (2021), who found that it positively impacts students' employability development.

Professional Examination Status

Professionals perceive licenses as instrumental for securing positions, maintaining employment, and effectively presenting their credentials. Simultaneously, educational institutions consider licenses as a vital indication of an individual's qualifications and legal authorization to engage in specific roles within the educational domain. Additionally, the performance of the individuals on the Licensure Examination for Teachers reflects their readiness as future teachers. A low pass rate in the LET indicates possible weaknesses in the standard of teacher education programs for pre-service teachers. Moreover, consistent poor performance on the LET can contribute to a decline in overall educational standards within a country (Guinayen, 2023). In essence, the quality of teacher preparation, as measured by the LET results, was closely linked to the broader educational outcomes and standards of a nation. Thus, if an individual cannot take the exam, it becomes impossible for them to enter the field of education.

Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK)

Employing technology skills in learning, as associated with TPACK, enhances teachers' confidence in their technological proficiency for 21st-century education. The study of Cabero (2019) pinpointed the relevance of pedagogical and content knowledge in ICT teacher training, given their noted complexity for educators. The model posits that effective ICT utilization in teaching necessitates instructor proficiency in technological, content, and pedagogical domains. The TPACK model helps incorporate digital media and tools into the process (Vaerenwyck et al., 2017), as adopted by Colon et al. (2023). Additionally, Matli et al. (2020) emphasized that digital literacy is a key skill that job seekers must possess to improve their chances of securing continuous job opportunities. Khan et al. (2022) further highlighted that critical skills, collaborative learning systems, and digital literacy enhance both academic performance and employability, underscoring the relevance of TPACK in preparing educators for the modern job market. As noted by Jita & Sintema (2022), knowledge of ICT integration is increasingly seen as a prerequisite for securing employment in education. Thus, teachers' ability to adapt to the technological demands of their profession is directly linked to their employability, making TPACK a pivotal framework for addressing the needs of the modern workforce.

Research Method:

This study aimed to determine the employability of the Graduates of Bachelor of Elementary Education students in Mandaue City College.

Design

In this study, a descriptive design type of research was utilized. It is the process of gathering and interpreting numerical data, claims Voxco (2021). The study utilizes descriptive design because the data can be presented through mere discussion and then looking for relationships between them.

For this study, A quantitative research methodology involves gathering and interpreting numerical data, enabling the identification of patterns, prediction-making, testing causal links, and extending findings to broader populations (Bhandari, 2023). This approach is favored when variables can be readily quantified using statistical methods.

Environment

Mandaue City College, the only educational institution in Mandaue City, is known for its commitment to accessible education and continuous improvement of its facilities. This study marks the institution's first tracer study for its Bachelor of Elementary Education program. The institution envisions future graduates empowering students to unleash their full potential, fostering productivity, and cultivating a generation of globally competitive leaders.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates in Mandaue City College from A.Y. 2016-2023.

A stratified sampling technique was employed, wherein it includes selecting sample with specific proportions from different subpopulations (strata) in the larger population (Arnab, 2017). Convenient sampling, on the other hand, this technique chooses participants based on ease of access, such as geographical proximity or willingness to participate in the study.

Instrument

The questionnaire used by the researcher was a modified questionnaire that was taken from Pentang et. al (2022), a standardized questionnaire that was taken from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), and Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) Kurt (2019). It is the main instrument used in the gathering of data. The questions were all created to be closed-ended due to the descriptive-quantitative nature of the research study. The questionnaire was structured into three sections: first section finds out the demographic data on employability, second section covers the respondents' educational profile, and the third assesses skills affecting employability based on the TPACK model.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before collecting data, the researchers have gone through a design hearing after Chapters 1 and 2 are written. They adhered to the panelists' feedback and recommendations after careful review. Upon approval, the researchers received a notice to proceed certificate and prepared a request letter to Mandaue City College. After obtaining approval from the School Dean and teachers, they conducted a brief orientation and allowed respondents ample time to complete the online survey.

Additionally, the researchers then sent a transmittal letter to the school head of Mandaue City College to acquire permission for the study. Upon receiving approval from higher authorities, the research team proceeded with conducting an online survey. an online survey via Google Forms distributed through social media platforms. The respondents' signed a certificate of confidentiality and informed consent that signifies the voluntary agreement of the participants to take part in the research study.

After gathering the data, the researchers tabulated and analyzed the given data of responses for interpretation, which were validated by a counter-checker. Conclusions and recommendations were drawn from the analysis. The Google Form link was deleted two weeks after the data collection concluded.

Data Analysis

The data gathered was analyzed using appropriate statistical tools, such as frequency distribution and mean, for descriptive questions. A Likert scale was employed to assess the employability of BEED graduates from Mandaue City College. Frequency distribution was calculated by tallying responses based on the Likert scale. On the other hand, simple percentage was computed by dividing the number of responses by the total responses and multiplying by 100. The weighted mean was also used to interpret the employability data, with stratified convenient sampling applied to determine the respondents.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the study, all responses were anonymous, and data collected were treated as strongly confidential. No identities or private information was gathered. The responses and raw data were stored on a password-protected laptop and the completed surveys were preserved in a locked cabinet. The study's findings were tabulated and presented in tables to prevent respondents' identification.

Findings and Discussion:

This chapter presented the results, the analysis, and the interpretation of data gathered from the answers to the questionnaires distributed online. The data were presented in tabular form following the specific questions posited in the statement on the problem.

Table 1: Academic Profile

This table which can be found on the next page shows the academic profile of the respondents such as their reasons for taking the education profession, honors and awards received, as well as their performance in LET exam.

The table shows what the respondents said about why they chose to study the teaching profession. Their reasons for taking the teacher education are the influence of parents and relatives 30 responses with a percentage of (19.48%). Moreover, most of the honors and awards they received were government scholarships with 19 responses with a percentage of (34.54%). Lastly, most of the respondents are LET passers with 29 (55.77%) while 9 (17.31 %) are waiting for the LET schedule, and only 5 (9.61%) did not pass the LET exam. The data shows the significance of family influence, as shown in the high percentage of LET passers among the respondents.

Meanwhile, Li et al. (2022) discovered that academic performance is crucial in predicting college students' employability by mediating achievement motivation. It was also supported by the study of Lacay et al. (2023), The majority of graduates who answered their study, or 64.82% of all respondents, were Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) passers. It likewise followed the pattern in the Philippines, where new graduates took the LET as one of the most popular licensing exams (Cabahug, 2017).

ACADEMIC PROFILE		
Reasons for taking the teacher education profession	Frequency	Percentage
Strong passion for the profession	29	18.83
Influence of parents and relatives	30	19.48
Inspired by a role model	24	15.58
Good grades in the high school	4	2.59
Availability of course offerings in the chosen institution	18	11.68
Prospect immediate employment	3	1.95
High grades in the subject area related to the course	5	3.25
Availability of scholarship grant of the course	3	1.95
Prospect of career advancement	6	3.90
Peer influence	9	5.84
Prospect of attractive compensation	6	3.90
Status or prestige of the profession	5	3.25
Opportunity for employment abroad	6	3.90
No choice or no better idea	6	3.90
Honors and Awards Received		
Government scholarship (DOST/CHED/LGU)	19	34.54
Private/NGO scholarship	4	7.27
Academic Excellence	16	29.09
Leadership/Service/Athlete Awardee	8	14.55
None	8	14.55
LET Performance		
Passers	29	55.77
Waiting LET Schedule	9	17.31
Never took LET Exam	9	17.31
Did not pass the LET Exam	5	9.61

Table 2

This table which can be found on the next page. This table shows the employment of the respondents such as the importance of their preparation with their current employment and the competencies found useful in their current job. Highlighted in this table are the respondents' current employment. About half of them (48.08%) think their education matches their job, while the other half (51.92%) do not. On the other hand, the competencies found useful in a current job

are communication skills, which got the highest percentage of 17.67%, while entrepreneurial skills got the lowest percentage of 6.90%. This means that although not all the respondents may think that education fits their job perfectly, acquiring communication skills is essential to obtaining and maintaining employment.

This result is similar to the study of Palattao et al. (2021), wherein they highlighted the importance of developing these soft skills to optimize students' future employability. This outcome strongly predicts improved employability for graduates in today's dynamic and demanding global job market by enhancing the curriculum at Mandaue City College.

Relationship of College Preparation and Current Job	Frequency	Percentage
Relevance of Current Preparation with Current Employment		
Related	25	48.08
Not Related	27	51.92
Competencies Found Useful in Current Job		
Communication Skills	41	17.67
Problem-Solving Skills	31	13.36
Human Relation Skill	35	15.09
Information Technology Skills	32	13.79
Critical thinking Information technology Skills	27	11.64
Technical Skills	23	9.91
Entrepreneurial Skills	16	6.90
	27	11.64

**Multiple Response*

Table 3: Problems and difficulties encountered in securing employment Job

This table outlines the respondents' challenges and difficulties in securing employment in their current jobs. The difficulties in securing employment include ranking standards (26.57%), limited training opportunities (21.09%), lack of teaching experience (20.31%), restrictive work settings (14.84%), and limited availability of teaching positions (10.16%). On the other hand, respondents generally do not perceive the absence of established linkages as a significant issue. In their current employment, the problems they encountered were numerous forms/reports and paperwork got the highest percentage of 18%, and more designation and daily routine got the lowest percentage of 10%. This means that finding a job can be hard, also there are a lot of problems they encounter in their present job. In alignment with Patimo et al. (2019), the issue of unemployment due to lack of experience resonates in the education sector, particularly for recent teacher graduates. Patimo et al.'s study underscores the urgency for robust employment support systems, especially crucial for educators grappling with limited experience securing teaching roles.

Problems and Difficulties Encountered	Frequency	Percentage
Difficulties Encountered in Securing Employment		
Ranking Standard	34	26.57
Limited Training Attended	27	21.09
Lack of Teaching Experience	26	20.31
Work Setting	19	14.84
Limited Teaching Positions	13	10.16
No Linkages Established	9	7.03
Problems Encountered in the Present Job		
Numerous forms/Reports and Paper Works	18	18
Poor and Unstable Internet Connection	8	8
Conflict with Management	17	17
Work Setting	6	6
Lack of Technical Skills	15	15
Relationship with colleagues and management	5	5
Field Mismatch	6	6
License Renewal on Present Job	10	10
Job Dissatisfaction	2	2
Unemployed	8	8
More Designations	1	1
Daily Routine	1	1
None	1	1

Multiple Response

Table 4: Employment Data

This table shows the employment status of the respondents such as their present employment status and present occupation. It indicates in the table that the respondents' employment data.

Employment data	Frequency	Percentage
Presently Employed		
Yes	42	80.77
No	10	19.23
TOTAL	52	100
Present employment status		
Regular or permanent	29	69.05
Temporary	3	7.14
Contractual	8	19.05
Casual	2	4.76
Self-employed	0	0
TOTAL	42	100
Present Occupation		
Accounting Staff	2	4.76
Accounts Payable Specialist	1	2.38
Branch Cashier	2	4.76
Branch Associate	1	2.38
Call Center	5	11.91
Data Encoder	1	2.38
ECE Teacher	1	2.38
Educational Assistance	1	2.38
Elementary Teacher	6	14.29
English as Second Language Teacher	6	14.29
Factory Worker	1	2.38
Faculty Staff	2	4.76
HR Assistant	1	2.38
MAPEH Coordinator	1	2.38
Micro Finance Officer	1	2.38
Physical Therapy Technician	1	2.38
Private Teacher	1	2.38
Processing Analyst	2	4.76
Public Teacher	1	2.38
Stock Control Clerk	1	2.38
TOTAL	42	100

The data revealed that the majority of the respondents are presently employed. In terms of their occupation, aside from teaching, it is also evident that there are diverse opportunities available to respondents, such as call center and office staff roles. It shows that graduates have a range of career options available to them beyond their initial field of study. As supported by the study of Calamayo (2022), the College's course offerings are commendable as they meet the needs of the local community and the demand for employment opportunities, thereby enhancing graduates' chances of securing jobs and ultimately improving the economic conditions of citizens. This approach qualifies them for a diverse range of job opportunities in the real world.

Table 5: Reasons why not yet employed or never been employed

This table which can be seen on the next page where it is only applicable to unemployed respondents where it shows the respondents' reasons for employment such as reasons why they are not yet employed or have never been employed.

The results substantiate that 40% of respondents attribute their unemployment to pursuing graduate studies, while 10% of respondents had insufficient work experience, and an equal number were raising their children. This result affirms that the dominance of continuing education as a reason for unemployment suggests both individual aspirations for personal and professional development. According to Gentova et al. (2023), graduates pursued graduate studies to attain professional and personal growth.

Reasons why not yet employed / never been employed	Frequency	Percentage
Advanced or Further Study	4	40
Family Concern and decided not to find a job	3	30
Lack of Work Experience	1	10
No Job Opportunity	0	0
Did not Look for a Job	0	0
Taking good care of my child and having small business	1	10
Family Choice	1	10
TOTAL	10	100

Thus, these graduates see an opportunity to grow and develop their professional and personal being as it allows them to continue their needs as professionals.

Table 6: Curriculum in College Relevant to First Job

This table is only applicable to employed respondents' where it talks about whether the college curriculum is relevant to their first job or not.

Was the curriculum you had in college relevant to your first job?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	27	64.3
No	15	35.7
TOTAL	42	100

Based on the table the highest percentage, 64.3%, corresponds to students who answer yes, followed by a slight decrease to 35.7%, who answer No. It proved how college curricula are relevant in their first job. According to Sumagaysay (2020), when asked about the relevance of their college curriculum to their first job, respondents affirmed that the curriculum was indeed relevant.

Table 7: Competencies in college found useful

This table shows competencies in college found useful in the respondents' first job.

What competencies learned in college did you find very useful in your first job? You may check (/) more than one answer.	Frequency	Percentage
Communication skills	27	29.35
Critical Thinking skills	23	25
Entrepreneurial skills	7	7.60
Human Relations skills	16	17.39
Problem-solving skills	18	19.57
Mindful Skills and Curriculum Development	1	1.09
*Multiple response		

It presents the frequency of what competencies they learned in their study years that are useful in their first job, the majority is communication skills at 29.35%, followed by critical thinking skills at 25%, then problem-solving skills at 19.57%, then human relations skills at 17.39%, and then entrepreneurial skills with 7.60%, lastly the mindful skills and curriculum Development with 1.09%. According to Tayco et al (2022), the study indicates that the curriculum and skills acquired by NORSU graduates apply to their employment. Respondents recognize the value of competencies like communication, human relations, critical thinking, and problem-solving.

Table 8: Suggestions for Improving Course Curriculum

This table is only applicable to employed respondents where it shows the respondents' suggestions for improving the course Curriculum.

Suggestions to further improve your course curriculum	Frequency	Percentage
Teaching Strategies and Skills	14	33.33
Career and Job Pursuit	4	9.53
Training and Preparation	7	16.67
Communication and Language Skills	7	16.67
Time Management and Resources	5	11.90
No Specific Suggestion	5	11.90
TOTAL	42	100

Based on the table the suggestion to further improve their course curriculum 33.33% answered the teaching strategies and skills, then followed by 16.67% with the same percentage, who answered the training and preparation, and communication and language skills, and followed by 11.90% with the same percentage, who answered time management and resources, and no specific suggestion, and lastly, 9.53% answered about career and job pursuit. Bernate et al (2024) the evolution of

inventive teaching methodologies within academic settings is crucial for enhancing competencies. Moreover, it underscores the feasibility of implementing teaching strategies that blend theoretical and practical approaches, tailored to the focus and thematic contents of subjects.

This approach streamlines the assimilation and adoption of requisite knowledge by future graduates, thereby underscoring the imperative to integrate innovative tools aimed at fostering knowledge appropriation to better equip professionals in the field of Physical Education.

Table 9: Technology Knowledge

This table shows the Technology, Pedagogy, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of the respondents.

TK (Technology Knowledge)	WM	DE
1. I know how to solve my own technical problems	3.19	A
2. I can learn technology easily	3.05	A
3. I keep up with important new technologies	3.23	A
4. I frequently play around the technology	3.01	A
5. I know about a lot of different technologies	2.80	A
6. I have the technical skills I need to use technology	3.09	A
AWM	3.06	A

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76-2.50 – Disagree (D), 2.51-3.25 – Agree (A), 3.26 - 4.00 - SA (Strongly Agree), WM-Weighted Mean, DE-Descriptive Equivalent, AWM-Average Weighted Mean

In technology knowledge, it was found out that on average, they know how to navigate technology since it received the lowest score of 2.80 indicating a frequency described as “agree” This means that graduates know how to navigate different technology. Hence, there is still a challenge that they may face while navigating the technology. As supported by the study of Cabero (2019) emphasized the importance of pedagogical and content knowledge in ICT teacher training, as these areas were found to be the most challenging for educators. On the other hand, statement number 3 “I keep up with important new technologies” got the highest weighted mean of 3.23 indicating a frequency as described as “agree” It shows that individuals are actively updated with the ever-evolving technological advancement. This means that technology can have a huge impact on the employability of the respondents. As stated by Jita & Sintema (2022), knowledge about ICT integration is needed to land a job in education.

Table 10: Pedagogical Knowledge

This table shows the Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) of the respondents.

PK (Pedagogical Knowledge)	WM	DE
19. I know how to assist students’ performance in a classroom	3.28	SA
20. I can adapt my teaching based upon what students currently understand or do not understand	3.28	SA
21. I can adapt my teaching style to different learners	3.25	A
22. I can assist student learning in multiple ways	3.25	A
23. I can use a wide range of teaching approaches in a classroom setting	3.23	A
24. I am familiar with common students’ understanding and misconceptions	3.15	A
25. I know how to organize and maintain classroom management	3.25	A
AWM	3.24	A

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76-2.50 – Disagree (D), 2.51-3.25 – Agree (A), 3.26 – 4.00 – SA (Strongly Agree), WM-Weighted Mean, DE-Descriptive Equivalent, AWM-Average Weighted Mean

In this table it was found that on average, they can acknowledge and affirm their familiarity with these aspects of student learning since it received the lowest weighted mean of 3.15 indicating a frequency of “agree”. On the other hand, statements number 19 and 20 “I know how to assist students’ performance in a classroom “ and “I possess the ability to enhance students' performance in a classroom" and "I am capable of adjusting my teaching methods according to students' current comprehension levels" received the highest weighted mean of 3.28, signifying a consensus of "strongly agree."

This suggests a significant level of pedagogical competence and adaptability, empowering the teacher to customize their methods to effectively address the varied needs of their students. As supported by the study of Sarina (2021), the importance of continuous professional development and adaptability to the needs of learners enhances the learning process of students if the teaching style is suitable to their needs and interests.

Table 11: Pedagogical Content Knowledge

This table shows the Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) of the respondents.

PCK (Pedagogical Content Knowledge)	WM	DE
26. I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning in mathematics	2.90	A
27. I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning literacy	3.07	A
28. I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning in science	3.03	A
29. I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning in social studies	3	A
AWM	3	A

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76-2.50 – Disagree (D), 2.51-3.25 – Agree (A), 3.26 – 4.00 – SA (Strongly Agree), WM-Weighted Mean, DE-Descriptive Equivalent, AWM-Average Weighted Mean

This table shows the pedagogical content knowledge, it was found that statement number 29 “I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning in mathematics” got the lowest score of 2.90 indicating a frequency of “agree” which means that they may have some familiarity with selecting teaching approaches for mathematics but may lack confidence or expertise in doing so effectively.

On the other hand, the statement of number 27 “I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning literacy” got the highest weighted mean of 3.07 indicating a frequency of “agree” This indicates that they possess a strong understanding of effective pedagogical approaches tailored specifically to the domain of literacy. They likely have experience and expertise in selecting strategies that promote critical thinking, comprehension, and communication skills among students. It was also mentioned in the study of Khan et al. (2022) that most of teachers in literacy engage in different teaching techniques and strategies that develop the student’s critical thinking, communication, and creativity.

Table 12: Technological Content Knowledge

This table shows the Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) of the respondents.

TCK (Technological Content Knowledge)	WM	DE
30. I know about technologies that I can use for understanding and doing mathematics	2.88	A
31. I know about technologies that I can use for understanding and doing literacy	3.17	A
32. I know about technologies that I can use for understanding and doing science	3	A
33. I know about technologies that I can use for understanding and doing social studies	3.03	A
AWM	3.02	A

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76-2.50 – Disagree (D), 2.51-3.25 – Agree (A), 3.26 - 4.00 - SA (Strongly Agree), WM-Weighted Mean, DE-Descriptive Equivalent, AWM-Average Weighted Mean

In this table of technological content knowledge, it was found that the respondents possess some knowledge of technologies that can aid in comprehending and performing mathematical tasks. However, it received the lowest weighted mean score of 2.88 indicating a frequency of “agree”. It indicates that while the person has some familiarity with relevant technologies for mathematics, their understanding or proficiency in this area is relatively low compared to other areas evaluated.

On the other hand, this statement shows the result that the person has familiarity with technologies useful for understanding and engaging with literacy-related activities. It achieved the highest weighted mean score of 3.17, indicating a frequency of “agree”. This implies that most respondents acknowledged the importance of having technological familiarity for engaging with literacy-related activities. Thus, technology can play an important role in supporting and sustaining change in literacy teaching and learning where teachers are more creative in classroom activities (Mckenly,2017).

Table 13: Technological Pedagogical Knowledge

This table shows the Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) of the respondents.

This table can be found on the next page where it presents the technological pedagogical knowledge, it was found that the respondents believe they can take on leadership, roles in facilitating the coordination of content, technologies, and teaching methods within their school or district. However, it received a relatively low score of 3.11, indicating a frequency of “agree.” It implies that while the individual acknowledges their potential to provide leadership in this aspect, there may be some doubts or reservations among respondents about the extent of their ability or readiness to effectively carry out this role. Additionally, it was also found out in this table that statements numbers 36 and 38, both statements received the highest weighted mean score of 3.32, indicating a frequency of "strongly agree". It implies that respondents strongly endorse the idea that the individual's teacher education program has successfully prompted them to consider the influence of technology on teaching approaches. Additionally, respondents strongly agree that the individual can adapt learned technologies to different teaching activities. As supported by the study of Hooper (2017), teachers who learn to integrate technology may go on to re-conceptualize their roles in the classroom.

TPK (Technological Pedagogical Knowledge)	WM	DE
34. I can choose technologies that enhance the teaching approaches for a lesson	3.30	SA
35. I can choose technologies that enhance students' learning for a lesson	3.28	SA
36. My teacher education program has caused me to think more deeply about how technology called influence the teaching approaches I use in my classroom	3.32	SA
37. I am thinking critically about how to use technology in my classroom	3.26	SA
38. I can adapt the use of the technologies that I am learning about to different teaching activities	3.32	SA
39. I can select technologies to use in my classroom that enhance what I teach, how I teach what students learn	3.23	A
40. I can use strategies that combined content, technologies, and teaching approaches that I learned about in my course work in my classroom	3.21	A
41. I can provide leadership in helping others to coordinate the use of content, technologies, and teaching approaches at my school and /or district	3.11	A
42. I can choose technologies that enhance the content for a lesson	3.19	A
AWM	3.25	A

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76-2.50 – Disagree (D), 2.51-3.25 – Agree

(A), 3.26 - 4.00 - SA (Strongly Agree), WM-Weighted Mean, DE-Descriptive Equivalent,

AWM-Average Weighted Mean.

Table 14: Technology Pedagogy and Content Knowledge

This table can be found on the next page where it shows the Technology Pedagogy and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of the respondents.

TPACK (Technology Pedagogy and Content Knowledge)	WM	DE
43. I can teach lessons that appropriately combine mathematics, technologies, and teaching approaches	2.96	A
44. I can teach lessons that appropriately combine literacy, technologies, and teaching approaches	3.11	A
45. I can teach lessons that appropriately combine science, technologies, and teaching approaches	3.09	A
46. I can teach lessons that appropriately combine social studies, technologies, and teaching approaches	3.09	A
AWM	3.06	A

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76-2.50 – Disagree (D), 2.51-3.25 – Agree (A), 3.26 - 4.00 - SA (Strongly Agree), WM-Weighted Mean, DE-Descriptive Equivalent, AWM-Average Weighted Mean

This table presents the technology pedagogy and content knowledge, it was found that the respondents feel capable of delivering lessons that effectively integrate mathematics, technologies, and various teaching methods. However, it received a relatively low weighted mean score of 2.96, indicating a frequency of "agree". On the other hand, it was also found in this table that respondents feel confident in their ability to deliver lessons that effectively integrate literacy, technologies, and various teaching methods. It received the highest weighted mean score of 3.11, indicating a frequency of "agree" among respondents.

This implies that the individual's peers or evaluators generally believe in their capacity to teach lessons that successfully blend literacy, technologies, and teaching approaches. The higher score suggests a stronger endorsement and confidence in the individual's proficiency in this specific area compared to other statements evaluated. It indicates that the individual likely has a solid understanding and ability to integrate these elements seamlessly into their teaching practice. It was also mentioned in the study of Akram et, al. (2022), that teachers exhibit positive perceptions regarding technology integration in different subjects in teaching learning practices.

Conclusion:

The researchers concluded that 21st-century skills and soft skills are factors contributing to their employability. These skills are crucial for securing employment in today's competitive job market because they enable individuals to navigate complex work environments, communicate effectively, and contribute to team success.

Limitations and Further Research:

This study is limited to graduates of the BEED program from Mandaue City College. It includes both regular and irregular students, as well as transferees who completed their degree at Mandaue City College.

Based on the implications highlighted in the findings and conclusion of this study, it is evident that 21st-century teaching skills and soft skills are crucial in the Employability of the Bachelor of Elementary Graduates. To further improve these skills, the recommendations are suggested;

For BEED Graduates, utilization of the checklists to be used as an exit assessment for the BEED program. This is to assess if the graduating students have already acquired certain 21st-century skills related to teaching.

For Institutions, should prioritize hiring instructors proficient in 21st-century teaching methods. These educators can impart skills essential for addressing the learning needs of digitally savvy students. This approach enhances the educational experience and prepares students for success in the digital age.

For Instructors, should prioritize helping the students develop their soft skills, which are vital in the real world. Through these useful skills, they can do better at work and can handle all kinds of situations confidently.

For BEED alumni, should attend continuing professional development and various teaching training programs right after graduation because it is crucial in today's world. These opportunities provide invaluable knowledge and skills necessary

for effective teaching. By staying updated on teaching trends and enhancing their teaching abilities, future educators can ensure the delivery of high-quality education to the students. All education graduates are required to participate in a tracer study during their credential transactions at the school. This mandatory involvement serves as a crucial tool for the institution to accurately assess the employability of the graduates and determine the underlying factors contributing to their employment status.

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